

Digitizing and Comparing Halegannada Manuscripts through Deep Learning and Classical Machine Learning Techniques

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Abstract: This paper presents a character recognition system for Halegannada manuscripts using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Support Vector Machines (SVM), and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) to automate the transcription of ancient Kannada texts. Addressing challenges like complex ligatures and handwriting variability, the approach follows a pipeline of preprocessing, segmentation, and classification using separate models for Base Characters, Modifiers, and Ottakshara. CNN achieved test accuracies of 98%, 97%, and 99%, showing strong generalization and faster recognition. While SVM attained slightly higher accuracies—99%, 98%, and 100%—it showed signs of overfitting and slower inference. KNN performed moderately with 86%, 94%, and 98%. The results highlight CNN as the most balanced and scalable approach for ancient script digitization, supporting the preservation of Halegannada manuscripts.

Keywords— Halegannada, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM) Kannada OCR.

I. INTRODUCTION

The digitization and recognition of ancient scripts have become critical for preserving cultural heritage and enabling computational analysis of historical texts, a field gaining momentum in recent years. Halegannada, an ancient precursor to the modern Kannada script, is a valuable resource for linguistic and historical studies, yet its manual transcription is hindered by degraded manuscripts and diverse handwriting styles. Computational approaches have shown promise in addressing such challenges, with efforts to translate Halegannada poetry into Hosagannada demonstrating the potential of automated systems [1]. Reviews of ancient Kannada text recognition further underscore the effectiveness of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for feature extraction and classification in similar contexts [2].

Advancements in handwritten text recognition highlight both progress and persistent obstacles, such as noise, script complexity, and dataset variability [3]. These challenges are evident across various scripts, with deep learning techniques like CNNs being applied to recognize Devanagari characters through quadrant-based analysis or intricate feature extraction, offering insights applicable to Halegannada [4], [7], [8]. Similar approaches have been adapted for other ancient scripts, including palm-leaf manuscripts in Tamil [9], Balinese [10], and Telugu [19], as well as MODI [11] and Ethiopian scripts [12], showcasing CNNs' versatility in handling diverse writing systems. Preprocessing techniques, such as noise removal from

damaged manuscripts, are equally vital, with studies emphasizing their role in enhancing recognition accuracy for historical documents [5], [13].

CNN-based optical character recognition (OCR) has proven adaptable to scripts like Ashokan Brahmi [6], Tibetan [16], and medieval Gurmukhi [18], often integrating advanced architectures or hybrid models to improve performance. Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) have complemented CNNs in recognizing Devanagari and Bengali scripts through zoning techniques [15], while attention-based models have tackled Japanese historical documents [17]. Data mining of ancient script images [14] and computer-assisted transcription with lexicon constraints [20] further illustrate the breadth of methodologies in this domain.

Building upon these foundations, this paper presents a CNN-based character recognition system specifically trained to identify Halegannada script from manuscripts dating between the 13th and 17th centuries. Similar to modern Kannada, Halegannada includes base characters, vowel modifiers, and ottaksharas (consonant conjuncts), which may appear independently or in complex combinations, complicating recognition efforts. The proposed system preprocesses manuscript images, segments characters into components, and utilizes specialized CNN models to classify them, thereby producing accurate digital representations of Halegannada text. This work contributes to the digital preservation of Halegannada and provides a scalable framework for recognizing ancient South Indian scripts.

II. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for recognizing Halegannada characters involves a multi-step pipeline, from data collection to model training, designed to handle the complexities of ancient manuscripts. The process, outlined in Fig. 1, encompasses preprocessing noisy images, segmenting characters into their components, and classifying them using tailored Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs).

A. Data Collection

A dataset of Halegannada manuscripts was collected by photographing physical documents, including palm-leaf scripts obtained from the University of Mysore. The dataset captures a diverse range of handwriting styles and manuscript conditions, providing a rich foundation for experimentation and analysis.

B. Preprocessing

Raw manuscript images were subjected to a series of preprocessing steps to improve character legibility. First, grayscale conversion was applied, followed by adaptive thresholding to transform the images into a binary (black-and-white) format, enhancing contrast between text and background. Gaussian and median filters were then used to reduce noise, such as ink smudges or paper imperfections, common in historical documents. These steps ensured that subsequent segmentation and recognition tasks operated on cleaner inputs, addressing challenges noted in handwritten text recognition surveys.

Fig. 1. Methodology flowchart

C. Letter Segmentation

A custom segmentation algorithm was developed to isolate individual characters from the preprocessed images. The algorithm utilized character dilation with a filter size of (2,1) and Gaussian noise addition with a filter of (1,1) to enhance character boundaries before applying contour detection using OpenCV.

Fig. 2. CNN Model Architecture

Fig. 3. Segmented character with Base character ,modifier and ottakshara

Contours were then analyzed with a rule-based approach to categorize segments into base characters, modifiers, or

ottaksharas as shown Fig 2. This method effectively accounted for the combinatorial nature of Halegannada, where a single glyph might include a base character with an attached modifier and/or ottakshara. Segmented characters as shown in Fig 3, were manually verified and grouped into a labeled dataset, capturing variations in style and handwriting, similar to feature extraction techniques used for Devanagari scripts.

After segmentation process white pixel padding were done with 8 pixel width. Then these were augmented to extend the dataset and these characters were sorted into 3 different directories (Base Character, Modifier, Ottakshara) number of classes and instances or images are mentioned table 1.

Dataset	Total number of images	Number of classes
Base Character	6143	42
Modifier	2057	14
Ottakshara	2170	22

Table 1: Image and Classes per Dataset

D. CNN Model Design

The given image represents a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture designed for character recognition in Halegannada manuscripts. The system consists of three specialized CNN or KNN or SVM models to recognize different character components as shown in Fig 4:

Fig. 4. Character segmentation pipeline

1. Base Character Model: Identifies standalone consonants or vowels.
2. Modifier Model: Detects vowel modifiers attached to base characters.
3. Ottakshara Model: Recognizes consonant modifiers (ottaksharas) above base characters.

Outputs from these 3 models are combined, these done by addition of their Unicode values as demonstrated.

$$\text{Kannada character} = (B + V + O) + M \quad \text{--- (Eq 1)}$$

Where, B = Base character, V = Virama (◌̣), O = Ottakshara (consonant conjunct), M = Modifier (like vowel signs, anusvara, visarga, etc.), here parenthesis in equation signify order of addition.

Architecture Overview: All three models have same CNN architecture the only difference they hold is number of output nodes as shown Fig 5.

1. Input Layer (64x64x1)

The input image has a resolution of 64x64 pixels with a single channel (grayscale).

2. First Convolutional Layer (Conv 3x3x32): A 3x3 convolutional filter extracts 32 feature maps, capturing small patterns in the image.

Fig. 5. CNN Model Architecture

3. Second Convolutional Layer (Conv 3x3x64): Another 3x3 filter extracts 64 feature maps, identifying more complex structures.

4. Branching into Three Convolutional Layers:

- Conv 1x1x64: A 1x1 convolution layer used for dimensionality reduction and feature mixing.
- Conv 3x3x32: A standard 3x3 convolution, refining feature extraction.
- Conv 5x5x32: A 5x5 convolution, capturing broader spatial patterns.

5. Fully Connected (FC) Layers:

- FC 128: A fully connected layer with 128 neurons, converting features into a dense representation.
- FC Softmax: The final layer applies the Softmax activation function for classification.

This model is designed get fine to large feature and classify based on these features extracted.

E. Training Details & Overfitting Prevention:

To mitigate overfitting, techniques inspired by CNN applications in ancient script recognition were employed. Hyperparameter tuning was performed experimentally,

setting the learning rate to 0.001 and batch size to 64 to optimize model performance. The CNN architecture, with its parallel convolution paths, enables effective feature extraction from Halegannada characters, balancing fine details and broad spatial structures for accurate recognition.

The dataset was split into 80% training and 20% validation sets. Models were trained using the Adam optimizer and categorical cross-entropy loss over 50 epochs, with early stopping to halt training if validation loss plateaued. Performance was assessed using accuracy and loss metrics on both training and validation sets, following standard practices in CNN-based OCR systems. Results and Discussion

The three CNN models demonstrated robust performance across their respective tasks, as detailed below:

F. Training results:

Training accuracy and loss, Validation accuracy and loss are summarized in Table 2.

Fig 6: Base character training characteristics

• Base Character Model:

Training Accuracy: 93.07%, Training Loss: 0.3286 Validation Accuracy: 97.47%, Validation Loss: 0.2002 as shown in Fig 6, the sharp spikes in graph are a result of large patience value of 20, epoch 40 and transfer learning. This model effectively identified standalone characters, though it occasionally struggled with highly stylized or degraded glyphs, a challenge consistent with findings in handwritten text recognition.

Fig 7: Modifier character training characteristics

- **Modifier Model:**

Training Accuracy: 96.91%, Training Loss: 0.2222
 Validation Accuracy: 97.08%, Validation Loss: 0.22 as shown in Fig 7, the sharp spikes in graph are a result of large patience value of 20, epoch 40 and transfer learning. The high accuracy reflects the simpler structure of modifiers, with errors primarily occurring in cases of overlapping strokes, aligning with observations in Devanagari recognition.

- **Ottakshara Model:**

Fig 8: Ottakshara character training characteristics

Training Accuracy: 99.71%, Training Loss: 0.0992
 Validation Accuracy: 99.93%, Validation Loss: 0.0874 as shown in Fig 8, the sharp spikes in graph are a result of large patience value of 20, epoch 40 and transfer learning. Near-perfect performance was achieved due to the distinct placement and limited variability of ottaksharas, corroborating CNN efficacy for small, localized features.

All the training performance metrics are summarized under the table 1.

Model	Training accuracy	Training loss	Validation accuracy	Validation loss
Base character model	0.9307	0.3286	0.9747	0.2002
Modifier model	0.9691	0.2222	0.9708	0.2207
Ottakshara model	0.9971	0.0992	0.9993	0.0874

Table 2: Training Results Summary

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) with 5 neighbors and Euclidean distance, and Support Vector Machine (SVM) with an RBF kernel (C=10, gamma='scale') were also trained on the same dataset for classifying base characters, modifiers, and ottaksharas.

G. Testing results:

The performance of the three classification models Base Character, Modifier and Ottakshara has been evaluated using weighted precision, recall, F1 score, and test accuracy, based on their respective test datasets, as shown in Table 3.

The CNN-based Base Character model, evaluated on a test set of 6,143 images, achieved a weighted precision of 0.9787, recall of 0.9781, and an F1 score of 0.9781, with an overall test accuracy of 98%, indicating robust and consistent performance across diverse character classes. The Modifier model, tested on 2,057 images, showed a weighted precision and recall of 0.9713, and an F1 score of 0.9710, reflecting strong generalization capability across different modifier symbols, with a test accuracy of 97%. Remarkably, the Ottakshara model, evaluated on 2,170 images, achieved near-perfect performance with a precision of 0.9996, recall of 0.9995, and F1 score of 0.9995, demonstrating exceptional reliability and classification accuracy for ottakshara components.

Model	Model	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Test accuracy
CNN	Base character model	0.9787	0.9781	0.9781	0.98
	Modifier model	0.9713	0.9713	0.9710	0.97
	Ottakshara model	0.9996	0.9995	0.9995	0.99
SVM	Base character model	0.9935	0.9747	0.9934	0.99
	Modifier model	0.9745	0.9747	0.9744	0.98
	Ottakshara model	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
KNN	Base character model	0.8695	0.8606	0.8615	0.86
	Modifier model	0.9383	0.9358	0.9363	0.94
	Ottakshara model	0.9860	0.9829	0.9837	0.98

Table 3: Testing Results Summary

In addition to the CNN models, Support Vector Machine (SVM) and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) classifiers were also trained and evaluated on the same datasets to serve as comparative baselines. The SVM models, using an RBF kernel (C=10, gamma='scale'), showed competitive performance, especially for the Ottakshara class, achieving perfect precision, recall, F1 score, and 100% test accuracy. The Base Character and Modifier SVM models also performed well, with F1 scores of 0.9934 and 0.9744, respectively. Conversely, the KNN models, configured with 5 neighbors and using the Euclidean distance metric, yielded comparatively lower performance, particularly in the Base Character classification (F1 score of 0.8615 and 86% accuracy), although they demonstrated respectable results for

the Modifier and Ottakshara classes, with F1 scores of 0.9363 and 0.9837, respectively. These comparisons highlight the superior performance and reliability of the CNN-based models, especially for complex classes like Ottakshara.

Weighted Performance Metric Equations

The weighted metrics account for label imbalance by incorporating the number of instances (support) for each class, using the following formulas:

• Weighted Precision = $\sum (P_i \times s_i) / \sum s_i$ (Eq 2)

, for all class n

• Weighted Recall = $\sum (R_i \times s_i) / \sum s_i$ (Eq 3)

, for all class n

• Weighted F1 Score = $\sum (F1_i \times s_i) / \sum s_i$ (Eq 4)

, for all class n

Where:

- P_i , R_i , and $F1_i$ are the precision, recall, and F1 score for class i.
- s_i is the number of true instances (support) for class i.
- n is the total number of classes.

These results highlight the effectiveness and robustness of the models within their specific classification domains, with the Ottakshara model standing out for its near-flawless performance.

H. Results discussion for overall pipeline:

The test image contains full Kannada characters, each composed of a base character, a modifier, and optionally an Ottakshara (conjunct). As discussed earlier, the same segmented character image is passed through three separate models trained to recognize base, modifier, and Ottakshara components respectively. Each model outputs a Unicode character, and these are combined using Unicode addition to reconstruct the full character.

CNN:
 ಬಳಿತವಂಗಾದಳೋರ್ವಳ್ಳಡದಿಪಿಡಿನಡೆಯ
 ಚಲುವೆಚಂದುಟಿಯಂದಗಾತಿಕೊಡಮೊಲೆಯಕೋ
 ಮಲೆನಿತಂಬದನಿತಂಬದನೀರಪುರುಳಿನುಡಿಯರಳೆಗಲ್ಪುರುಣೀಮಣೀ
 ಗಿಳಿದೇರನರಸಿಯಳಮುಂಗೈಗಿಣಿಯೊಳೆಸವ
 ಲಲನೆಯಳಚಂದ್ರಮತಿಯಂಬುವಳವೆರೆಯುತಸು
 ಸಿಲಸೊಗಮನನುಭವಿಸುತೊಪ್ಪಿದಂಪಲವುದಿನಮಸುರಪತಿಯತಿಮುದದೊಳೊ

SVM:
 ಬಳಿತವಂಗಾದಳೋರ್ವಳ್ಳಡದಿಪಿಡಿನಡೆಯ
 ಚಲಿವೆಚಂದುಟಿಯಂದಗಾತಿಕೊಡಮೊಲೆಯಕೋ
 ಮಲೆನಿತಂಬದನಿತಂಬದನೀರಪುರುಳಿನುಡಿಯರಳೆಗಲ್ಪುರುಣೀಮಣೀ
 ಗಿಳಿದೇರನರಸಿಯಳಮುಂಗೈಗಿಣಿಯೊಳೆಸವ
 ಲಲನೆಯಳಚಂದ್ರಮತಿಯಂಬುವಳವೆರೆಯುತಸು
 ಸಿಲಸೊಗಮನನುಭವಿಸುತೊಪ್ಪಿದಂಪಲವುದಿನಮಸುರಪತಿಯತಿಮುದದೊಳೊ

KNN:
 ಬಳಿತವಂಗಾದಳೋರ್ವಳ್ಳಡದಿಪಿಡಿನಡೆಯ
 ಚಲುವೆಚಂದುಟಿಯಂದಗಾತಿಕೊಡಮೊಲೆಯಕೋ
 ಸುಲೆನಿತಂಬದನಿತಂಬದನೀತಪುರುಳಿನುಡಿಯರಳೆಗಲ್ಪುರುಣೀಮಣೀ
 ಗಿಳಿದೇರನರಸಿಯಳಮುಂಗೈಗಿಣಿಯೊಳೆಸವ
 ಲಲನೆಯಳಚಂದ್ರಮತಿಯಂಬುವಳವೆರೆಯುತಸು
 ಸಿಲಸೊಗಮನನುಭವಿಸುತೊಪ್ಪಿದಂಪಲವುದಿನಮಸುರಪತಿಯತಿಮುದದೊಳೊ

Fig. 9. Model Outputs

This process is repeated in a loop over all segmented character images from the dataset to generate the complete sentence. This modular approach ensures high accuracy while simplifying training and handling the complexity of Kannada script recognition effectively. The outcomes of the combined model pipeline for 3 different models are shown in Fig 9 and can be compared with Fig 10. Fig 10 represents the expected output, manually transcribed by a Halegannada language expert with reference to the original manuscript. In contrast, Fig 8 displays the output generated by the model when given the raw manuscript image as input.

Expected:
 ಬಳಿತವಂಗಾದಳೋರ್ವಳ್ಳ ಮಡದಿ ಪಿಡಿನಡೆಯ
 ಚಲುವೆ ಚಂದುಟಿಯಂದಗಾತಿ ಕೊಡಮೊಲೆಯ ಕೋ
 ಮಲೆ ನಿತಂಬದ ನಿತಂಬದ ನೀರ ಪುರುಳಿನುಡಿಯರಳೆಗಲ್ಪು ತರುಣೀಮಣಿ
 ಗಿಳಿದೇರನರಸಿಯೊಳ ಮುಂಗೈಗಿಣಿಯೊಳೆಸವ
 ಲಲನೆಯಳ ಚಂದ್ರಮತಿಯಂಬುವಳವೆರೆಯುತ ಸು
 ಸಿಲ ಸೊಗಮನನುಭವಿಸುತೊಪ್ಪಿದಂ ಪಲವುದಿನಮಸುರಪತಿಯ ಮುದದೊಳೊ

Fig. 10. Expected Output

In terms of recognition accuracy, the SVM model produced the most accurate match with the expected output, closely replicating the sentence with minimal errors. However, this high accuracy can be attributed to overfitting on the training dataset, as the model appears to have memorized patterns rather than generalizing across variations. This makes SVM ideal for highly similar or structured data but potentially less reliable on unseen or diverse inputs. In contrast, the CNN model, while showing slightly more character-level deviations compared to SVM, demonstrated better generalization, managing to accurately predict most characters even with subtle distortions and variations. It maintained a strong structural and semantic similarity with the expected output, reflecting a robust capacity to handle complex or noisy inputs. The KNN model, however, showed the weakest correctness, with frequent errors and less coherent sentence construction, indicating limited ability to capture complex character relationships.

CNN:
 Total Recognition time: 16.6704 seconds
 Recognition time per character: 0.1366 seconds

SVM:
 Total Recognition time: 5.8599 seconds
 Recognition time per character: 0.0480 seconds

KNN:
 Total Recognition time: 69.1904 seconds
 Recognition time per character: 0.5671 seconds

Fig 11: Execution time

From a timing perspective, SVM achieved the fastest recognition speed, with a total recognition time of 5.86 seconds and 0.0480 seconds per character, which is highly suitable for real-time applications. However, this speed advantage may also reflect its inflexibility or overfitting behavior. CNN, on the other hand, balanced speed and accuracy well, completing recognition in 16.67 seconds with 0.1366 seconds per character, while maintaining better adaptability across character variations. The KNN model was significantly slower, requiring 69.19 seconds in total (0.5671

seconds per character), due to its non-parametric nature and computational inefficiency at inference time. This renders KNN less practical for large-scale or real-time applications despite moderate accuracy in some cases.

III. NOVELTY OF WORK

This work introduces a statistical segmentation method combined with CNN, SVM, and KNN-based classification techniques for Halegannada manuscripts. A modular pipeline separates base characters, modifiers, and Ottakshara, allowing easy updates to individual components. Multiple classifiers were explored to improve recognition accuracy and robustness, with CNN providing deep feature learning, while SVM and KNN offered complementary pattern recognition strategies. The use of Unicode-based recombination to reconstruct complex characters, along with a looped decoding approach to generate complete sentences from segmented lines, makes the system adaptable and practical for digitizing ancient scripts.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

This study demonstrates the effectiveness of deep learning, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), in recognizing complex characters from Halegannada manuscripts. Among the three evaluated models CNN, SVM, and KNN the CNN model achieved a strong balance between recognition accuracy and inference time. While the SVM model delivered the highest accuracy in certain subcategories (e.g., Ottakshara), its performance is indicative of overfitting, with limited generalization potential. Conversely, CNN consistently showed robust performance across all categories (Base, Modifier, and Ottakshara), effectively generalizing to character variations present in the test data. The KNN model, though simple and intuitive, underperformed both in accuracy and recognition time, making it less suitable for practical deployment.

The character-level recognition results further reinforced the strength of CNN in handling script variability and noise typical of scanned or digitized manuscripts. While SVM achieved slightly higher accuracy in controlled scenarios, its overfitting tendency and dependency on parameter tuning make CNN the more scalable and adaptable solution for real-world applications.

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